

Effect of geometric imperfections on compression of back-to-back I-beam columns with modified cross-sectional shape - numerical study

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ABSTRACT

This article is a continuation of Aleksandra Pawlak's article entitled "Effect of geometric imperfections on compression of back-to-back I-beam columns with modified cross-sectional shape - scanning and experimental tests." Research into thin-walled cold-formed structures continues to attract interest because of their favourable strength-to-weight ratio, environmental friendliness and numerous applications, for example in modular construction. This paper presents compression tests of thin-walled I-beam columns. These columns are constructed of thin-walled channels with modified cross-sectional shapes connected back-to-back by sheet metal screws. 3D scanning technique was used to create a numerical model with real geometric imperfections. Nonlinear finite element analysis was performed. The FE model included a nonlinear material model and frictional contact between the webs of the channels. The performed investigation indicate that geometric imperfections have a significant effect on the values of critical forces and the load-bearing capacity of the tested columns. For the proposed new sections of I-beams, significantly higher strength properties were obtained with respect to an ordinary I-beam constructed from lipped channels.

Keywords: buckling, compression, FEM, imperfections

1 INTRODUCTION

This article is a continuation of Aleksandra Pawlak's article entitled "Effect of geometric imperfections on compression of back-to-back I-beam columns with modified cross-sectional shape - scanning and experimental tests." Thin-walled structural elements, due to their high strength properties with relatively low weight, are part of modern trends of sustainable development. The lightness of such structures resulting from the much smaller amount of material required for their manufacture significantly reduces their carbon footprint. For example, producing one ton of steel emits about 1.832 tons of CO₂, so reducing the weight of structures through their efficient design contributes to lower manufacturing costs and a smaller carbon footprint. Paczos, in an article [1], presented thin-walled beams with modified channel cross-sections, whose load-bearing capacity increased by several hundred percent relative to classical channels with only a few tens of percent increase in their weight. Thin-walled structures are increasingly used in modular construction as wall and floor elements, in production halls, bridges and as components of transmission towers. An extensive description of the applications, fabrication techniques, design and optimization of cold-formed thin-walled structures is contained in works [2,3]. Thin-walled structures also have disadvantages that limit their applicability. The high slenderness of thin-walled structures determines their significant susceptibility to loss of stability. The problem of loss of stability has been described in detail in works [4,5,6,7]. Geometric and material imperfections are another issue affecting the load-bearing capacity and stability of structures. The effect of geometric imperfections on the critical buckling load of axially compressed I-beam columns was studied by Szymczak and Kujawa in their paper [8]. The article [9] describes the characterization and modeling of geometric imperfections.

Structural elements such as I-beams cannot be made directly by cold-forming. They are formed as web-jointed channels. Recently, a lot of research work is being done on how to connect, strength and stability of such structures along with consideration of their geometric imperfections. In papers [10,11], the bending and compression of back-to-back I-beams were studied experimentally and numerically. In order to search for I-beams with higher load-bearing capacity, new I-beam columns constructed from channels with modified cross-sections are presented and studied in this work. The purpose of this work is to study the effect of geometric imperfections on the stability and load-bearing capacity of the tested columns, and to show that the critical forces and load-bearing capacity for the proposed columns with modified cross sections are significantly higher than these strength properties relative to classical back-to-back built-up cold-formed steel lipped channel columns.

2 SUBJECT OF THE RESEARCH

The subjects of this study are thin-walled I-sections formed from channel webs joined by sheet metal screws. The shapes and dimensions of their ideal cross sections are shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Subject of the research

The thickness of the sheet from which the tested columns are made is equal to 0.5 mm. The strength properties of DX51 steel were assumed according to the results obtained from the static tensile test, the results obtained are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Mechanical properties of DX51 steel obtained on the basis of a static tensile test

Mechanical property	Symbol	Value
Young's modulus	E	181 GPa
Upper yield point	R_{eH}	330 MPa
Tensile strength	R_m	380 MPa
Poisson's ratio	ν	0.3

The actual columns were properly prepared and scanned with an iReal-3D scanner, and then converted into a cad model which was used in the numerical study. Photos of the scanning station and an example of the cad model of the scanned column are shown in Figure 2.

Fig. 2. Scanning 3D: scanning station, cross-section of 2T3 column, CAD model.

3 NUMERICAL STUDY – FINITE ELEMENT METHOD

Numerical studies were carried out using the finite element method with Ansys software. The columns were modelled with the second order quadratic shell elements with 8 nodes and parabolic edges. Triangular shell elements with 6 nodes and parabolic edges were used at the hole locations. Shell elements were used in the model due to the fact that the studied columns are thin-walled elements. All 6 degrees of freedom were blocked in the base of the column. At the top of the column, all rotations were blocked, as well as translations in directions perpendicular to the column axis. The boundary conditions are shown in Figure 3. The compressive load was set using Remote Displacement of the upper end of the column. The model used a contact-type connection between the connected webs of the compressed columns with a friction coefficient of 0.15. A finite element mesh (Figure 3) with element sizes equal to 5mm was used. Convergence analysis of the mesh showed that the discretization error does not exceed 2%.

Fig. 3 Details of FE model: a) boundary conditions; b) details of the mesh

Two nonlinear analyses were performed for 2T1-2T3 columns. The first for ideal beams with an initial geometric imperfection determined from a linear buckling analysis. The magnitude of the initial imperfection was equal to 20% of the thickness of the plate from which the columns were made. The second nonlinear analysis was carried out for columns with actual imperfections obtained from the 3D scanning method.

Figure 4 shows an example of the results of the nonlinear analysis of the local form of loss of stability for column 2T1 with imperfections obtained using linear buckling analysis.

Fig.4 Local form of buckling of a compressed 2T1 column with initial imperfections

Due to the thin-walled nature of the tested columns (thickness of 0.5 mm), the shape of geometric imperfections has a significant impact on the forms of buckling and the values of critical forces.

Fig.5 Local form of buckling of a compressed 2T1 column with real imperfections

Figure 5 shows the buckling form for column 2T1 with real imperfections. It can be seen that there is a significant difference between the buckling forms for columns with imperfections derived from linear analysis and real imperfections. The averaged strain method was used to determine the critical force as shown in Figure 6 for column 2T1 with real imperfections.

Fig.6 Method of determining the critical force for a 2T1 column with real imperfections

The values of critical forces obtained for the studied columns from experiment (F_{cr}^{EXP}), nonlinear analysis with initial imperfections (F_{cr}^{ID}) and nonlinear analysis with actual imperfections (F_{cr}^R) are shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Critical force values

Column	F_{cr}^{EXP} [kN]	F_{cr}^R [kN]	F_{cr}^{ID} [kN]
2T1	5.01	6,4	9,8
2T2	10.04	14,8	25
2T3	18.45	19,5	27,6

Analysis of the obtained results indicates that the lowest values of critical forces were obtained experimentally, which may be influenced by some material imperfections that arise in the numerical bending process causing anisotropy of sheet properties that is not considered in the numerical model.

Critical force values obtained for real columns are more than 30% lower than those obtained for ideal columns with initial imperfections derived from linear buckling analysis.

Fig. 7 Failure mode for 2T3 column: with initial imperfections (top), with real imperfections (bottom)

Figure 7 shows the forms of failure of the compressed columns. It can be seen that for the column with initial imperfections, the web was destroyed first and foremost, while for the column with real imperfections, the column flange was also destroyed, indicating that geometric imperfections affect not only the load-bearing capacity values, but also the failure mode of the columns. The graphs of the compression force as a function of the shortening of the columns are shown in Figure 8.

Fig. 8 Graph of compression force as a function of the shortening of the columns 2T2 with real imperfections

A comparison of the values of the maximum forces obtained in the experiment and numerical studies is shown in Table 3.

Table 3. Maximum force values

Column	F_{max}^{EXP} [kN]	F_{max}^R [kN]	F_{max}^{ID} [kN]
2T1	10,04	22,76	21,47
2T2	39,1	53,63	75,41
2T3	46,9	57,5	90,62

From the analysis of the results, it can be seen that, also for the maximum forces, the lowest values were obtained in experimental studies, while the highest values were obtained in numerical studies for ideal models with initial imperfections. The exception is section 2T1 for which the obtained column load-bearing capacities are similar for both numerical models.

4 CONCLUSION

The main conclusion are:

1. The results obtained in the study indicate that geometric imperfections have a significant effect on both the forms of buckling and failure, as well as on the values of critical and maximum forces of the compressed columns.
2. The real imperfections have a more unfavourable effect on the stability and load carrying capacity of the tested columns than the initial imperfections obtained by linear buckling analysis.
3. Numerical studies confirm the conclusion of the experimental studies preceding this article in which a much more favourable ratio of critical forces and load-bearing capacity to mass was indicated for columns 2T2 and 2T3 relative to the standard column 2T1.
4. Further numerical studies require consideration of the effect of material imperfections resulting from changes in material strength properties at the bends.

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